

‘Music transfigures Time’:

A case for phenomenological temporality in musical spectralism¹

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*Composers’ manipulation of temporality vis-à-vis the unfolding of musical time is central to the discipline and indeed the history of music is replete with differing methods and approaches to the potentials inherent in the manipulation of listener’s attention and expectation. In this essay I will address one such movement or approach entitled ‘spectralism’, which is based on analysis into the perception of sound itself as a means to create music and which espouses research into the spectral information contained in sounds as a compositional tool. To this end I will focus predominantly on the concept of temporality and, in particular, with the phenomenologist Maurice Merleau-Ponty’s (1908–1961) chapter on temporality in his book *The Phenomenology of Perception*.² I will begin by describing the main tenets of spectralism and draw parallels between the aesthetics of the composer Gérard Grisey (1946–1998) and Merleau-Ponty’s work in order to build arguments based on where they may be similar and where they may diverge. I will pose the question of: What a phenomenological perception of temporality would mean for the so-called ‘spectral’ aesthetics in Grisey’s music? I will then, in section two, attempt to criticise the analysis component of spectralism and see if it is compatible with Merleau-Ponty’s phenomenology. Finally, in section three, I will finish by addressing the question of: Whether the use of*

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² Part three, section II, ‘Temporality’ in Maurice Merleau-Ponty, *Phenomenology of Perception*, trans. Donald A. Landes (Abingdon, England; New York, NY: Routledge, 1945), 432–457.

musical 'temporalism' in the place of 'spectralism' is more suitable? Given the arguments provided.

Introduction & background

Spectralist composers, by making use of the Fourier series and Discrete Fast-Fourier Transforms – abbreviated DFFT – analysed, by computational means, the harmonic spectra – or component frequencies – which make up complex musical tones. These component frequencies – also called partials – when played together as simple sinusoidal waves, provide a somewhat rough approximation of the original complex sound or timbre. Indeed, this is the defining feature of additive synthesis.³ Composers seeing the potential in this approach of sonic analysis and instrumental re-synthesis have, in various music studios since the early experiments of the 1970s, focused on developing compositional techniques including the concepts of spectral morphology or how sounds change over time, temporal variations and of listener perception and retention. It is by examining the thought of spectral composers that, in the following section, I hope to address the temporality of the spectral style by asking the question of what are the phenomenological tenets of spectralism may be and how may they relate to the phenomenological thought of Merleau-Ponty?

1.

The application of the term 'spectral' to the early works of Gérard Grisey can be seen as defining a compositional aesthetic that was distinct from the serialist style prevalent in post-war Europe. The compositional techniques of spectralism being those informed by discoveries

³ For a more thorough account of the techniques of spectralism and the concept of timbre please see Joshua Fineberg, 'Guide to the basic concepts and techniques of spectral music', *Contemporary Music Review*, 19 no. 2 (2000), 81–113, DOI: 10.1080/07494460000640271.

and analysis into the fundamental nature of sound and musical tones as an impetus in the creation of new works. Although Grisey was by no means the only ‘spectral’ composer, he was one of the more prominent and outspoken ones. Despite this he rejected the term spectralism as being one which was too limiting in the context of his work and espoused instead the concepts of extended time and continuity as defining markers.⁴ In the posthumous journal article ‘Did you say spectral?’, he promotes this by stating that:

The temporal consequences [of spectralism] contain a more attentive attitude towards the phenomenology of perception, an integration of time as the very object of form and an exploration of “stretched” time and “contracted” time, separate from that of the rhythms of language.⁵

In an earlier article he discusses several strategies for temporal variation and offers a theory of scales of sound proximity.⁶ Where rate of change in material or sonic similarity between consecutive gestures may be carefully manipulated in order to expand and contract time.

These forces [sounds] - I purposely use this word and not the word form - are infinitely mobile and fluctuating; they are alive like cells, with a birth, life and death, and above all tend towards a continual transformation of their own energy. There exists no sound which is static, immobile, any more than the rock strata of mountains are immobile. By definition, we will say that sound is

⁴ David Bundler, ‘Interview with Gerard Grisey, 18 January 1996, Los Angeles’, Available at: <<http://www.angelfire.com/music2/davidbundler/grisey.html>> accessed 1 June 2020.

⁵ Grisey, ‘Did You Say Spectral?’, 2–3.

⁶ Gérard Grisey, ‘Tempus ex Machina: A composer's reflections on musical time’, trans. S. Welbourn, *Contemporary Music Review* 2 no. 1 (1987), 239–275, DOI: 10.1080/07494468708567060.

transitory. It is not defined by an isolated moment, nor by a series of isolated moments fastidiously realized and placed in sequence.⁷

Here we can see definite parallels with the thought of Merleau-Ponty, in that it is through the transitory nature of sound that we are able to perceive musical time. Merleau-Ponty writes that consecutive events are never the result of imperceptible transitions, but that they pass into each other and these changes are what constitutes time for the consciousness.

Instant C and instant D – as close together as one wishes to make them – are never indiscernible [sic], for then there would be no time at all; rather, they pass into each other, and C becomes D because it was never anything but the anticipation of D as present, and of its own passage into the past.⁸

In parallel with this, Grisey notes that, through manipulation of the degree of anticipation in composition, one can influence musical time.

By including not only the sound but, moreover, the differences perceived between sounds, the real material of the composer becomes the degree of predictability, or better, the degree of "preaudibility".
So, to influence the degree of preaudibility we come back to composing musical time directly - that is to say perceptible time, as opposed to Chronometric time...It is no longer the single sound whose density

⁷ Ibid., at 269.

⁸ Merleau-Ponty, *Phenomenology of Perception*, at 444.

will embody time, but rather the difference or lack of difference between one sound and its neighbour; in other words, the transition from the known to the unknown and the amount of information that each sound event introduces.⁹

If we are to translate this concept of pre-audibility into phenomenological terms, we find the concepts readily available in what Husserl termed ‘retention’ and ‘protention’.¹⁰ The term of retention being used to describe an established state of affairs – in our case a sound or sonic transition – related to deterministic causality and objects of perception at that time which leads to a ‘protention’, a term describing an imagined future process based on the expectation elucidated by the retention. Regarding this, Merleau-Ponty writes:

Our future is not built exclusively of conjectures and fantasies. Prior to what I see and what I perceive, there is certainly nothing visible any longer, but my world is carried along by intentional lines that trace out in advance at least the style of what is about to arrive.¹¹

Grisey suggests several ways of addressing his conception of retention and protention, as discussed, such as the following:

Let us imagine a sound event, A, followed by another event, B.
Between A and B exists what one calls the density of the present, a density which is not a constant but which expands and contracts

⁹ Grisey, ‘Tempus ex Machina’, at 258.

¹⁰ Discussed in ‘Part One, Section Three’ in Edmund Husserl, *On the Phenomenology of the Consciousness of Internal Time*, ed. and trans. J.B. Brough. (Dordrecht: Kluwer, 1893–1917), 98–126.

¹¹ Merleau-Ponty, *Phenomenology of Perception*, at 439.

according to the event. In effect, of the difference between A and B is virtually nil, in other words if the sound B is entirely predictable, time seems to move at a certain speed. By contrast, if the sound B is radically different, and virtually unpredictable, time unfolds at a different speed...

Chronometric time is never obliterated, but our perception of it can overshadow the linear aspect for a more or less brief instant.¹²

What we can see here is the causal efficacy of sonic events on our perception of time, this is influenced by both the temporal and spectral density – complexity in relation to regularity and periodicity of harmonic spectra – of sound events. Upon being confronted with a succession of sonic events we are forced, on hearing even the second one, to relate it to the first, and in turn, the third to the second and first and so on. In setting up expectations one can make use of the phenomenon of expectation and substitution to slow down or speed up time.

However, in the cases of a constant lack of confirmation or in delaying resolution indefinitely, the flow of time is almost imperceptible. This is manifest in cases where sonic events may be closely related to preceding ones or, in the case of serialism, as having a lack of spectral grounding or, as in the case with minimalism, material being repeated for long durations. Here it may be stated that small adjustments between held durations may be imperceptible in relation to the whole as distinct to the perceptibility of minute differences between shorter events. Grisey writes that:

As every musician has been able to see for himself, to maintain an equivalent sensation of difference whatever the duration, one must have a longer difference between long durations than between short

¹² Gérard Grisey, 'Tempus ex Machina', 258–259.

durations.¹³

As we have now examined the temporal dimensions of spectralism, it would be useful to examine the spectral aspects and, indeed, account for the reductionist approach in the analysis and genesis of sonic material by asking if the analytic origins or starting points of the spectral method pose a problem for Merleau-Ponty's argument?

2.

At first glance the original discoveries or distinguishing stylistic features of *musique spectrale* may seem at odds with the methods of Merleau-Pontyan phenomenology, indeed in *The Phenomenology of Perception* reductionist and intellectualist approaches are given a back seat and are challenged by Merleau-Ponty's arguments in favour of a perceptual hegemony. As Merleau-Ponty writes:

It [intellectualism] believes it establishes its analysis upon the proof of mathematical truth and not upon the naïve evidentness of the world: *habemus ideam veram* [we have a true idea].¹⁴

Some criticisms from a phenomenological perspective that may be raised would be to ask if the analysis of sound is to abstract sound from its material causality and reduce it to numbers? Given that the harmonic series is an abstract mathematical concept, which can be described by taking a vibrating string and dividing it into fractions based on the total length corresponding to an arithmetic series of $\{f(1), f(2) \dots f(N)\}$, f being the frequency of a waveform measured

¹³ Ibid., at 247.

¹⁴ Merleau-Ponty, *Phenomenology of Perception*, at 40.

as cycles per second or Hertz, then when we conceive of spectra we invariably arrive at a simplified notion that has little bearing on how complex, let alone simple sounds – in the physical world – are constructed.¹⁵

As mentioned in the introduction, the very construction of musical instruments and analysis of the harmonic series contained in their production of tones reinforces the argument that musical instruments are not mathematically aligned to the harmonic series but strive, through their development and conventional historical use to the creation of harmonic – see periodic – musical tones by *approximating* such an alignment to the harmonic series. For example, some partials may have differing amplitudes or phases to those of a theoretical nature.¹⁶ In addition, some spectra may have missing partials or fundamentals that may be present in theoretic spectra. As Joshua Fineberg notes, missing fundamentals may be psychoacoustically filled in by the listener in their absence: these being termed virtual fundamentals.¹⁷

Indeed, the aims of spectralism, as discussed, is not a classification system or a taxonomy of sounds per se but an investigation into the nature of sounds so that manipulations based on empirical evidence and not abstract schema¹⁸ may be used in the creation of new works.

¹⁵ Or indeed, on how we perceive sound.

¹⁶ This is illustrated in figure 1.

¹⁷ Fineberg, 'Guide to the basic concepts and techniques of spectral music', at 98.

¹⁸ In contrast to serialism.

Fig 1. This image shows the spectrogram of a recorded D note – circa 147 Hz – on a clarinet to the left of the centre line and a synthesised sawtooth wave – a waveform containing all theoretical partials at matching amplitude – to its right. Both spectra share the same fundamental frequency. Note that the spectra do not match up exactly, but approximately.

After having looked at the criticism of the apparent intellectualist approach to spectralism and showing how it may be seen as a creative impetus and not a defining feature¹⁹ in the style it may be appropriate to address the third question in relation our theme of temporality by asking whether the title of musical ‘temporalism’ in the place of ‘spectralism’ is more suitable?

¹⁹ Even though this distinction may be somewhat vague, I argue that there is in fact a distinction. For if we were to, through analysis and subsequent resynthesis, approximate the sounds of instruments then we are merely left with copies that may be akin to similar results arrived at from sampling and playback. Spectralism is more than the sum of its parts.

3.

If serialism's emancipation of dissonance can be said to contribute to the subversion of temporal relationships – whether intentional or not – then spectralism's avowal of temporal change and manipulations of perceptible procedural change provides a strong argument for the label of musical temporalism. Indeed, given the similarities in Grisey's and Merleau-Ponty's thought and the former's reluctance to accept the term spectralism, we are inclined to accept the new label, if that is, Merleau-Ponty may be labelled as a temporalist.

If we are to think of temporalism as a type of presentism and presentism as the opposite to eternalism, then eternalism would be, in turn, the opposite to temporalism.²⁰ Presentism relies on J.M.E. McTaggart's 'A-property' conception of time, as time being in possession of properties such as the present now; one day before now; one day after now.²¹ Thus, we can say that temporalism and presentism are synonymous.

For Merleau-Ponty the conception of temporalism is identical to McTaggart's A-series, in that perceived time and, in turn temporally present objects, when perceived by a temporally present observer are subject to the A-series' subjective conception of time, which McTaggart proposes is an essential condition to the possibility of time.²² The subjective conception of time espoused as an aesthetic parameter in spectralism lines up with this thought. It being a conception of musical time as a series of events in relation to the previous and defined by the present's retention and subsequent protention. Indeed, although the future is unconceivable in

²⁰ Based on and reductio ad absurdum argument of the concepts of temporalism, eternalism and time-indices in Ned Markosian, 'Time' in *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Autumn 2016 Edition)*, Edward N. Zalta (ed.), <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2016/entries/time/>> accessed 5 June 2020. In addition to Jeff Speaks, 'Theories of Meaning' in *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Spring 2020 Edition)*, Edward N. Zalta (ed.), <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2020/entries/meaning/>> accessed 5 June 2020.

²¹ Here I have paraphrased. McTaggart describes the A-series as 'the series of positions running from the far past through the near past to the present, and then from the present to the, near future and the far future' in J.M.E. McTaggart, 'The Unreality of Time', *Mind* 17, no. 68 (1908), 457–474.

²² As argued in Claudio Cormick, 'Against the "view from nowhen": A Merleau-Pontyan contribution to Dummett's approach to McTaggart's paradox', *Bulletin d'analyse phénoménologique* 10 no. 2 (2014), E-Journal, <<https://poppers.uliege.be/1782-2041/index.php?id=690>> accessed 7 June 2020.

musical time, it may be 'protented' from the past and present sonic events. Thus, I argue that we may say that musical spectralism, as described hitherto is indeed temporal.

It is certainly true that I could not perceive any temporal position without a before and an after; that, in order to apperceive the relation between the three terms, I must not merge with any one of them.²³

However, to change the stylistic moniker of spectralism to temporalism, as I see it, would be to unnecessarily complicate the matter, as it could prove troublesome to other styles sharing a similar temporal aesthetic. In addition, given the analytic starting points of spectralism as being investigations into timbre and sound spectra, such a name would prove to limit the designation of other styles or musical aesthetics as temporal.

Conclusion

The phenomenological aesthetics of spectralism, being partly timbral and harmonic have been shown – at least in the aesthetics of Grisey – to include a focus on the phenomenological aspects of memory and a temporal thought akin to that of Maurice Merleau-Ponty and, as demonstrated, have shown that the conscious experience of perceived time, as a creative parameter, can be subject to manipulation by musical means. The temporality of music has also shown to line up with the thought of other phenomenologies such as Husserl and McTaggart and is dependent on memory, duration and the difference and similarity in musical material. Although we may not be inclined to label musical spectralism as temporalism, it may be said

²³ Merleau-Ponty, *Phenomenology of Perception*, at 477.

that spectralism is indeed temporal and, thus, has temporality as one of its foci. As Merleau-Ponty writes:

We conceive of time before we conceive of its parts; temporal relations make events in time possible. Thus, correlatively, the subject must not himself be situated in time for him to be able to be present in intention to the past and to the future. Let us no longer say that time is a “given of consciousness,” but rather, more precisely, that consciousness unfolds or constitutes time. Through the ideality of time, consciousness finally ceases to be imprisoned in the present.²⁴

In closing, I argue that given spectralism’s conception of time and advocacy for manipulation of the latent possibilities in sound and musical tones, there is a strong case for the phenomenological aspects of temporality and thus, spectralism may be of a phenomenological nature by design.

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²⁴ Ibid., at 437.

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